

Evaluation of design properties of electric and combustion cars based on eye tracking

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The current transition to the electric car by all users is advancing steadily, and hence the design of these products occupies a prominent place in the car design sector. Likewise, the user experience is one of the determining aspects for the choice of a model. The main objective of this work is to determine, through eye tracking, which areas of an image (in this case, images of the front of cars) are more influential in the perception of the vehicle as either electric or combustion-powered, by segmenting the most important areas of a vehicle and users' perceptions thereof according to gender and other socio-demographic variables. This work provides an experimental design and a way to analyze and draw conclusions from an oculometry study for vehicles, as well as an initial design briefing for the generation of the visual identity of electric vehicles based on the perception of users for different elements of the vehicle. A methodology is proposed that includes the use of tools such as ANOVAs, eye-tracking, heat maps, tracking maps and fixation times. Through this data it is possible to develop optimal designs aligned with the user's perception.

Keywords: Eye tracking; electric car; design elements; aesthetics; styling; perceptual elements

1. Introduction

1. 1. Justification

The year 2021 was the fastest year of growth for electric cars worldwide. According to the official data, global electric car sales amounted to 4.2 million units, 108% more than in 2020, and 198% more than in 2019 (Jato Dynamics 2023). The promotion of the electric car therefore provides one way to address the mounting environmental and sustainability

challenges facing transportation (Rifkin 2011). Seba (2014) talks extensively about the transition to electric transport and how this can reduce carbon emissions and improve air quality (Seba 2014). This transition to electric transport also constitutes a way to lower dependence on oil and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Smil 2016; Mattick, Williams, and Allenby 2009).

Electrification of transport can play a major role in the transition to a more sustainable and cleaner energy system (Lovins, Odum, and Rowe 2013).

Decarbonization in the transport sector, especially in private mobility, is one of the main objectives of the European Union (EU) for the coming years. Battery electric vehicles represent a promising solution to reduce pollution and emissions; However, its purchase price contributes to slowing its spread. The results obtained show how the electricity consumption of electric vehicles is low, even for larger vehicles, and this allows them to be considered less impactful than vehicles with internal combustion engines (De Santis, Silvestri, and Forcina 2022).

Digalwar (Digalwar et al. 2022) shows how the Indian transportation sector powered by fossil fuels is mainly responsible for creating serious problems such as greenhouse gas emissions, dependence on foreign fuels, the economic burden and chronic health effects. To mitigate these serious problems, electric vehicles are positioned as an alternative, green and clean technology, which can potentially enable the efficient transition to a sustainable transportation system with low carbon emissions and the preservation of scarce natural resources.

1. 2. Background

The study by Sperling (2018) explores how the combination of automated, shared, and electric vehicles can enable a transition to a more sustainable, efficient, and accessible transport system. Electrification of transport can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and improve air quality in cities, and these technologies can influence urban design and the way people move around cities, with the aim of providing a holistic perspective on the transition to a more sustainable and efficient mobility (Sperling 2018).

Given the exponential trend in the decision to purchase electric vehicles, certain factors help consumers choose electric vehicles in preference to other types of vehicles, with environmental, social, and economic factors all playing a role.

Husain et al. (2021) have studied how consumers perceive the electric car and how automotive companies can design and market these vehicles to increase their market acceptance (Husain et al. 2021). They analyse the evolution of electric mobility, trends in the electric vehicle market, and companies' strategies to compete in this emerging market. Consumer perception of the electric car is examined, including attitudes towards the technology, assessment of product features, and barriers to electric vehicle adoption. Furthermore, topics such as charging infrastructure, government policy, and technological innovation in the automotive industry, are also covered.

Giesler (2006) explores how consumers construct meanings around technology through a process they call "consumer gift systems". In turn, manufacturers can use these meanings to enhance market acceptance of their products. Gift systems are cultural patterns that involve the transfer of material and symbolic goods between people, and that help shape the way consumers perceive and use products. Using the example of the electric car, it shows how consumers construct meanings around this product through a variety of gift systems, such as innovation, sustainability, and belonging to a community (Giesler 2006).

Consumers make decisions regarding the purchase of electric vehicles and the knowledge of how these decisions are made enables the design of policies and programmes to increase the market uptake of electric vehicles. In this vein, Vandenberg and Gilligan (2007) present a critical analysis of the role of human behaviour in environmental and sustainability-related decision-making and how this affects the uptake of electric vehicles. It is argued that consumers do not always make rational decisions based on self-interest, but are influenced by emotional, social, and cultural factors that can lead to unsustainable behaviour. Using the example of the electric car, the authors suggest that market acceptance of these vehicles can be increased through policies and programmes that promote accessibility, information, innovation,

and cooperation between the various stakeholders involved (Vandenbergh and Gilligan 2007). Another study by Dudenhöffer (2012) analyses the opportunities and risks of electric vehicles and provides a detailed assessment of the electric vehicle market. It uses a wide variety of data and statistics to show how consumers perceive electric vehicles and how car manufacturers can adapt to the needs of the market to increase their acceptance (Dudenhöffer 2012).

This study also confirms that the aesthetic properties of the vehicle can influence consumer perceptions of whether it is electric or combustion-powered, and these perceptions can be employed to improve the market acceptance of electric vehicles (Secinaro et al. 2022; Brase 2019).

The work developed by Rothenberger et al. (2012) investigates how the aesthetic properties of electric vehicle design can affect consumer perception of electric vehicle range and market acceptance. The study focuses on the design of the visual interface of the instrument panel of an electric vehicle and assesses how different visual designs affect the perception of vehicle range and consumer acceptance of electric vehicles. The results of the study suggest that a carefully designed visual design can improve the user experience and market acceptance of electric vehicles (Rothenberger et al. 2012).

There are numerous publications that have studied how the aesthetic properties of the car can affect consumer perceptions of whether it is electric or combustion-powered, and how these perceptions can be used to improve the market acceptance of electric vehicles. They address various aspects of user experience and acceptance of electric vehicles, and propose methodologies and approaches to improve usability, satisfaction, and adoption of electric vehicles in different contexts and cultures (Cocron et al. 2011; Chun et al. 2019; Curtale, Liao, and van der Waerden 2021; Burmann, Grzesiak, and Huang 2016).

Eye tracking (eye tracking or oculometry) is a technique used to measure and record the movement of a person's eyes and gaze while observing visual stimuli (products, images, videos, interfaces...). The main objective is to analyse how and where a person directs their visual

attention. Eye tracking is performed using devices called "eye trackers" that record the position and movement of the eyes. These trackers can usually be stand-alone cameras or devices built into special glasses. Some systems use infrared cameras to track the position of the pupils and calculate where the gaze is directed. In our case study, an independent infrared camera located in front of the respondent was used. In summary, eye tracking provides detailed information about users' visual behaviour and attention. Figure 1 shows in detail what the eye tracking methodology consists of.

Figure 1. Eyetracking methodology

The eye-tracking technique is applicable in various fields, including research in graphic design, advertising, user interfaces, and other areas related to visual perception and attention (Punde, Jadhav, and Manza 2017).

The book "Eye Tracking Methodology: Theory and Practice" discusses how eye tracking can be employed to determine which areas of an image or design are most relevant or appealing to

users, and how this information can be utilised to improve visual communication and user experience (Duchowski 2007).

There are computational models of visual attention based on the detection of saliency features in the image, such as edges, contrasts, and colours. Itti, Koch and Niebur (1998) used eye-tracking techniques to measure participants' eye movements while looking at natural and artificial images. The results showed that the proposed visual attention model was able to accurately predict the areas of the image that attracted the most visual attention of the participants (Itti, Koch, and Niebur 1998).

In the research conducted by Pajares, Rivas-Perea and Cruz (2013), eye-tracking techniques are employed to measure the distribution of participants' visual attention while observing images in conditions of reduced visibility. These authors also developed a computational model to predict visual perception and attention under various atmospheric conditions (Pajares, Rivas-Perea, and Cruz 2013).

In Ramanuja (2017), an emotional design model based on emotional evaluation theory is proposed. To validate the model, eye-tracking techniques were utilised to measure participants' visual attention while they looked at different product designs and evaluated their emotional appeal. The results showed that certain design features, such as symmetry and complexity, attracted participants' visual attention more and contributed to their emotional perception of design (Ramanujan 2017).

Eye tracking can be employed to analyse user interaction with complex visualisations, such as network graphs and flowcharts. Blascheck and Ertl (2014) used eye-tracking techniques where they measured participants' visual attention while exploring visualisations and developed a model to determine which areas of the visualisation were most important to the task at hand (Blascheck and Ertl 2014).

Finally, it is necessary to highlight how users' perceptions of the most important areas of a vehicle may vary according to gender and other socio-demographic variables. It has been studied how individual differences in perception and attention can affect the most important

areas of a vehicle, and how these findings can be utilised to improve design and user experience. Endsley (2016) addresses the importance of understanding individual differences in perception and attention when designing interactive systems, including vehicles, and strategies are offered to optimise situational awareness and user experience. Furthermore, said author discusses how technology, such as eye tracking, can help identify and understand these individual differences (Endsley 2016). Nowadays, it is always a challenge to study and interpret how gender differences can affect perception and attention in design in general and, for the particular case of vehicles, to analyse how these findings can be applied in order to improve the user experience since, depending on the gender of the person purchasing or driving the vehicle, one can have completely different needs and user experience (K. Li, Li, and Liu 2013).

Numerous publications have studied how cultural and socio-economic differences can affect the most important areas of a vehicle, and how these findings can be put to use to improve the design and user experience. In Thorandt et al. (2018), mixed reality technologies are utilised to design and evaluate a user-centred vehicle interior (Detjen et al. 2017). Sullivan et al. (2015) examine how demographic differences influence perceptions of design features of electric and internal combustion vehicles (Sullivan et al. 2015). Bhise et al. (2019) provide an overview of ergonomics and human factors in vehicle design, and highlight opportunities and challenges for the future (Bhise et al. 2019). In Thorandt et al. (2018), a methodology is presented for the design of user interfaces for electric vehicles that are adapted to the needs and preferences of users (Detjen et al. 2017). In Morris and Stanton (2013), the existing literature on designing vehicles for older drivers is reviewed and implications for future research are highlighted (Morris and Stanton 2013).

Some recent works have addressed real-life applications. In (Erdaş et al. 2023) structural optimization methods are used to carry out the optimal design of a seat support. As a result of the topology optimization, a new support design concept was created and used to optimize the shape.

Aye (Aye et al. 2019) seeks to design the shape and size of a crash box, to optimize resistance to car accidents, while the objective function is to maximize the total absorption of subject energy to a mass restriction. According to this study, the application of the proposed multiple surrogate model is better than using a traditional surrogate model in particular, especially for constrained optimization.

At (Yildirim et al. 2023) experimental and numerical collision analyzes are carried out to reach an optimal design of bumper beam and energy absorber for a passenger car. The models that are formed by using Taguchi tables are subjected to crash analysis and the answers are obtained to find an optimal design. As a result of the numerical analysis, a new model of energy absorber and bumper beam with better crash behavior and weight reduction.

The objective of this study of Yildiz (Yıldız 2020b) focuses on designing a new thin-walled energy absorber to be used in the design of electric vehicles. Presents an application of the slime mold algorithm to the optimal design of automotive components. Function evaluations are carried out using finite element analysis and estimated using the kriging surrogate model.

In this research, (Yıldız 2020a), a new hybrid salp swarm-Nelder-Mead (HSSA-NM) algorithm is developed to optimize electric vehicle components. Both the Latin hypercube sampling methodology and the radial basis function surrogate modeling approach are used to derive constraint equations and objectives used in shape optimization. As a result, a design problem is solved using HSSA-NM.

1.3. Hypotheses and objectives

As stated in the previous section, it is important to promote the electric car as an alternative measure for the reduction of pollution through green transport. The market is ready to accept the electric car since global sales have grown exponentially, according to the above data, and electric transport has been accepted as the best feasible and reliable alternative in the near future.

The following hypotheses are used as a starting point to develop the central objectives of this work:

1. The aesthetic properties of the vehicle influence its perception, and therefore affects the perception of the emerging electric car sector.
2. Eye tracking can be employed to determine which areas of interest (AOI) of an image (in this case images of vehicles) are most influential in the perception of the vehicle as electric or combustion powered.
3. The most important areas of a vehicle and users' perceptions thereof may differ according to gender and other socio-demographic variables.

The main objective of this work is to determine, through eye tracking, which areas of an image (in this case, images of the front of cars) are more influential in the perception of the vehicle as either electric or combustion-powered, by segmenting the most important areas of a vehicle and users' perceptions thereof according to gender and other socio-demographic variables.

The importance of deciding whether a car is either electric or combustion-powered for a user is because identity is an important area in the development of the styling of electric cars, with identity being what gives the product an individual character, unique, with a current style and adapted to the environment and circumstances of use. Product personality is based on the product's ability to differentiate itself from the competition. In relation to users, it is important to analyse their perception of electric vehicles, since being a new product it must seek to be recognizable by the rest of the users, thus marking a difference at a perceptual level with respect to traditional vehicles (Bennett and Vijaygopal 2018). Schuitema et al. (2013) analysed that owners of electric vehicles have emotions of pleasure and pride when owning an electric car, concluding that those people who have a pro-environmental self-identity are more likely to acquire an electric vehicle that enhances that self-identity and transmits it to others. others (Schuitema et al. 2013). From the point of view of the user of an electric car, it is important that he can communicate to other people that he is the owner of this type of vehicle since it helps

strengthen his self-image (Bennett and Vijaygopal 2018).

Through eye tracking, it will be determined which areas of an image (in this case vehicle images) most influence the perception of the vehicle as either electric or combustion-powered. The AOI (Areas Of Interest) that accumulate the most fixations in terms of surface size are assumed to be the most important for users when deciding whether a car is either electric or combustion-powered. It will also be studied how individual differences (based on gender and other socio-demographic variables) in perception and attention can affect the importance of AOIs.

The identity of the electric vehicle must be focused on enhancing those properties that give the electric car a differentiating character, in a way that allows the development of optimal designs aligned with the user's perception. The discussion herein provides ideas and suggestions for the development of optimal designs aligned with user perception.

Section 1.2 shows studies on how the aesthetic properties of the vehicle can affect consumers' perceptions of whether it is electric or combustion-powered, and how these perceptions can be employed to improve the acceptance of electric vehicles in the market. These publications address various aspects of user experience and acceptance of electric vehicles, and propose methodologies and approaches to improve usability, satisfaction, and adoption of electric vehicles in a variety of contexts and cultures.

To the best of our knowledge, there are no previous studies that integrate the aspects of segmenting the most important areas of car fronts and the users' perceptions thereof according to gender and other socio-demographic variables, and that, as a result of this segmentation, propose an identity of the electric vehicle focused on enhancing those properties that give the electric car a differentiating character. To this end, the ideas and suggestions provided herein for the development of optimal designs aligned with the perception of the user justify the research motivation of this work.

In the introduction to this work, an analysis of all the central aspects of the argumentation of the work is undertaken, which leads to the description in Section 2 of the methodological structure to be followed. Section 3 presents the results obtained from the experimentation, followed by a discussion of these results in Section 4. Section 5 contains the conclusions of all the research development carried out in this study.

2. Materials and methods

To achieve the objective of this work, as stated in the previous section, a methodological proposal is set out, based on the academic work analysed.

Reference texts are available regarding vehicle fronts (Chassy et al. 2015; Lu, Xu, and Cheng 2018). Likewise, there are studies on the lateral silhouettes of vehicles (Z. Li and Xia 2010; Chassy et al. 2015; Lu, Xu, and Cheng 2018; Lin, Guo, and Xu 2019; Hyun, Lee, and Kim 2017; Hyun et al. 2015; Luo et al. 2022; Huang, Ma, and Yang 2020).

A car is a product with complex shapes and each view has a large amount of information and properties specific to each view, which are often independent of the remaining views. The idea of this work involves studying the front of the vehicle and replicating this experiment for the side and rear views in future work. Given that there are reference texts on vehicle fronts, it has also been considered an opportunity to continue the work of other researchers. The front view has been chosen because it is a characteristic view in which the general public identifies the brand identity of the vehicle and other characteristics.

The methodology followed for this experiment is detailed in the following sections. Figure 2 shows the complete flowchart of the proposed methodology.

Figure 2. Proposed methodology

2.1. Defining attributes and levels

The first step is to define the attributes and levels of the proposed product. The attribute is the design parameter or design variable under study and the level represents the different values, options, or alternatives that the attribute can assume.

An extensive bibliographic study has been carried out on how other authors have selected the properties and levels.

In M. Li et al. (2020), a quantitative investigation is performed on the relationship between design elements and the style image of electric vehicles (M. Li et al. 2020). A combination of two techniques is applied to define property space: Morphological Analysis (called the classical method) and Protocol Analysis. The first strives to decompose a product (vehicle) into its main physical elements and the second carries out a verbal analysis of user interviews. This study works with 22 electric vehicles on the market, and, for the design elements, which are based on previous research, it establishes 5 characteristics of only the front of the vehicle, while with the verbal analysis of interviews it classifies the characteristic elements and their shape (Sun 2007).

In Xi et al. (2017), an investigation is carried out on the attractiveness of the shape of the electric vehicle. Twenty samples (letters) are used, with the focus on studying only the front of the vehicle (arbitrarily) (Xi et al. 2017). It takes images of the front of electric and traditional vehicles and conducts interviews in several phases to determine the “hot” components.

In Baroroh, Amalia, and Lestari (2019) a Kansei Engineering approach is used for the development of electric motorcycles (Baroroh, Amalia, and Lestari 2019). Design elements are selected from a comparative study (benchmarking) and 50 participants rank the 5 most important design parts (seat, bonnet, headlight, luggage rack, and frontal).

In (Suparmadi, Riyadi, and Junaidy 2021) (Suparmadi, Riyadi, and Junaidy 2021), the preferences of the Indonesian consumer regarding the design of electric motorcycles with Kansei Engineering are studied. 10 images are used and the various components of the motorcycle (style, handlebars, headlight, seat) and 3 view planes are generically selected based on a “validation test”, and factor analysis is applied.

In Zhang and Wang (2013) an application of Kansei Engineering in electric vehicle design is addressed (Zhang and Wang 2013). Through eye tracking and the display of vehicle images in 45° planes, the main design elements are determined: headlights, grille, bonnet, windscreen.

In Lai et al. (2022) Kansei Engineering is used for the exterior design of “new energy vehicles” through internet data mining (Lai et al. 2022). It uses internet data mining techniques to extract design features, Kansei words, relationships, etc. It uses a tracking application “Scrapy”, algorithms, and programming to collect data, on websites and forums related to the electric vehicle.

In Kang (2021) set theory and support vector regression are combined for the sustainable design of hybrid electric vehicles (HEV) for which 55 images of selected vehicles are used (Kang 2021). An interview with experts is proposed for the decomposition of the characteristic forms of HEV (morphological decomposition). Nine characteristic components are listed (rim,

side window, grille...) and classified into subtypes based on basic shape, so that users can evaluate "satisfaction".

In this case, a property space has been proposed that covers almost all the possible variation addressed in the reference texts. Furthermore, a formal aesthetic study has been carried out by the authors, which has resulted in the definitive choice of the properties and levels used in this work.

2.2. Defining attributes and levels of the design object

The sample space represents all the specific combinations of attribute levels that define each of the products under analysis.

The choice of attributes has been made based on their relationship and possible influence on the aesthetics and perception of the product. The proposal of key attributes has been made based on the reference texts and the objectives of the analysis itself. The definition of the attribute levels is the result of a market study of the current products offered by companies.

Specifically, the attributes and their levels under study in this work are: shape of the headlights (arc, double arch, thin, polygonal, rounded), separation of the headlights (yes, no), grille shape (long thin, organic, banner, polygonal, visual, without grille), frontal shape (big mouth, integrated, smile, U-type, without nerve). Therefore, the number of possible combinations or profiles to be obtained would be 2,700 ($5 \times 2 \times 6 \times 5 \times 3 \times 3$).

If the obtained sample space turns out to be too large (which is quite likely), it becomes unaffordable to process it in a survey. In the case of information overload due to such a high number of combinations, certain procedures exist that enable a reduction in the number of combinations to be presented to the respondent by limiting the confidence level of the parameters. In this case, the incorporation of Orthogonal Fractional Factorial Designs is proposed, which are utilised to reduce the number of profiles presented to users.

Therefore, a reduction of the sample space is proposed using orthogonal design. Figure 3 shows

the design process of an orthogonal experiment.

With the application of this technique, it is possible to obtain a representative and suitable fraction of all possible combinations of attribute levels (Xu et al. 2009). To carry out the fractional factorial design, the IBM SPSS Statistics v.26.0 software is applied using the “Orthogonal Design” function. The result of this application is the attainment of 49 profiles.

Figure 3. Design process of an orthogonal experiment Image adapted from J. Zhou et al. (Zhou et al. 2012)

2.3. Representing the sample space

The vehicle samples are created by graphic representation using images of real (commercial) vehicles. In these graphical representations, the background of the image, brand logos and badges, number plate data, and vehicle colour are removed, since these are elements that fall outside the scope of the study that may influence the perception and opinion of the respondents, thereby distorting the objective of the experiment.

2.4. Defining AOIs

For each stimulus (vehicle) to be analysed, areas of interest (AOIs) must be differentiated. The

AOIs are employed to divide the images that represent the stimuli and to obtain specific data of zones or areas of the graphic representation that help to improve the results by providing a greater level of detail. These areas must be clearly delimited in each of the images obtained.

2.5. Conducting experiments

The number of respondents has been based on a study on similar experiments, as detailed in the discussion section entitled "Regarding the sample size used for the experiment ". It must be considered that this is a pilot study carried out at the university level and at this time there is no professional or business support that may entail extrapolating the experiment to a larger population. For reasons of budget, space and time, a larger sample could not be included.

Numerous reference texts have been analysed and are found to seldom use a very large sample size. Therefore, it is considered that the sample size used herein of 33 participants is highly suitable for this type of experiment.

The results of eye tracking do not depend so much on the number of respondents but on the population under study, that is, on the demographic characteristics, the participants' previous experiences and interest in the product, since these can influence their gaze patterns. . For example, age, gender, experience and hobby in relation to the automotive field can be relevant variables.

It must be said that an eye tracking study can be influenced by the visual stimuli, the environmental context, the eye tracking technology, the design of the experiment, the data analyses used and the objectives of the study. The experiment for all participants has been carried out under the same environmental context, with the same eye tracking technology and with the same visual stimuli, following the same experimental procedure and sharing the same objective. The participants are all legal age and are familiar with the vehicles.

At the beginning of the experiment, the researchers explain the test procedure as well as the objectives of the study prior to the experiment. The users are also asked in writing for their

consent and informed that the data collected is anonymous and will only be used for this study and that they can leave the test at any time.

2.5.1 User test

A user test is carried out based on the closed interview education technique: in this case a multi-choice questionnaire with different single response alternatives is used.

The purpose of the test questions is twofold:

- P1 and P2: categorisation of the user based on gender and age.
- Q3 to Q7: analysis of the relationship between the respondent and the object of study.

Variables	Categories
Sex	Female Male
Age	Between 18 and 21 Between 22 and 25 Over 25
Driving licence	Yes In process
Ecological choice	Yes No
Purchase preference for a 100%-electric vehicle	Price Automatic Cargo volume Brand Power
Desire to purchase a 100%-electric vehicle	Yes No
Ability to differentiate a 100%-electric vehicle	Yes In doubt No

Table 1. Variables and categories of the user test

Due to the anonymous nature of the survey, instead of directly asking the users their age, the user test presents 3 age groups (between 18 and 21, between 22 and 25, and over 25).

On the other hand, the survey, carried out mainly with students in these age ranges, can give us information on whether they are probably in the 1st or 2nd academic year (18 to 21 years old), in the 3rd or 4th year (22 to 25 years old), or whether these are respondents who are probably not students (over 25 years old).

Out of the 33 participants, 8 are between 18 and 21 years old, 9 are between 22 and 25 and 16 are over 25 years old (see Table 3).

2.5.2. Eye tracking

At the beginning of the eye-tracking experiment, prompts are provided to participants before they view each vehicle stimuli. The instructions provided out loud to the participants are read by the researcher and always provided in the same way. Specifically, the prompts are:

"In this part you will be presented with images, and you must respond out loud whether it is an electric car for you. Respond YES or NO when the image appears so that your response can be noted by the researcher".

This is followed by an eye-tracking experiment (Wang et al. 2023), in which respondents are shown the images, consisting of 49 stimuli.

The experiment is carried out using the OGAMA software (Voßkühler 2009) and the Gazepoint GP3 oculometry equipment (Sarraiya et al. 2019). The experiment settings have been:

- Screen size of eye-tracker monitor is "x size"=1024 pixels and "y size"=768 pixels.
- Sampling rates = 60 Hz.
- Fixation calculation parameters:
 - Maximum distance in pixels that a point may vary from the average fixation point and still be considered part of the fixation = 60.
 - Minimum number of samples that can be considered a fixation = 3.
- Eliminate first fixation if it is at the same place as the last fixation of the foregoing trial and if it is shorter than 100ms.

Each stimulus (vehicle image) is displayed for 5000ms. Between stimuli, a blank screen

appears for 1000ms.

The total duration of the oculometry experiment is 293000ms (4.9 minutes). In

this experiment, the data collected includes:

- Fixations (count) for all AOIs
- Total Fixation Duration Mean (ms) for all AOIs
- Fixation duration mean at each AOI and Number of fixations (count) at each AOI
- % of total area of total picture area covered by the area of interest (AOIs)

2.5.3. Vehicle-type identification

During the eye-tracking experiment, in which respondents are shown images of different vehicles, they are asked to answer whether it appears to be an electric or combustion-powered car.

In this experiment, the data collected includes:

- Hits and misses in vehicle recognition

2.6. Descriptive analysis of the results

For the user test, an analysis of response frequencies, a correlation analysis between study variables, and ANOVAs between the variables that analyse the relationship between the respondent and the object of study, and the categorisation variables are carried out.

From the eye-tracking experiment, in the second phase of the proposed method, the number of fixations per AOI and the fixation duration per AOI are analysed, thereby obtaining the mean value, standard deviation, and maximum value, and heat maps and eye-tracking maps.

Fixations are moments when the eyes are relatively still, focused on a specific area. In our case study, a fixation was counted when the eye spent 300 ms in a specific area relatively still. The number of fixations in a specific area is called "Fixation count". The image that is generated to visualize the areas of the screen or image that receive more visual attention, that is, that receive more numbers of fixations, is called "Heat map".

Correlations between parameters of the eye-tracking experiment are attained.

From the third proposed phase, an ANOVA is performed to study the relationship between the numbers of hits and misses in the eye-tracking test and the type of vehicle (electric or combustion-powered).

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is based on the statistical assumptions of independence, normality, and homoscedasticity of the experimental responses (Villanueva, Petenate, and Da Silva 2000). It has been proven that the data meets ANOVA assumptions.

Specifically, the independence condition means that the observations in each group are independent of each other and the observations within groups were obtained by a random sample. Since, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no formal test available to verify that the observations in each group are independent and that they were obtained by a random sample, then the only way this assumption can be satisfied is if a randomised design is used. In our work, independence refers to the fact that a sample of fixations of one individual is independent of that of another, and that a randomised design has been used.

The ANOVA analysis were carried out using SPSS, with the one-factor ANOVA analysis module. The database has 32 case studies, each of them corresponding to the respondents (one of them was discarded due to an error in the measurement of one of the eyetracking parameters).

There are two groups of variables:

- 1) Qualitative or nominal variables: user test questions
- 2) Quantitative variables or scale: measurements obtained from eyetracking.

To treat the quantitative variables, it has been worked with the average of the responses provided by each respondent. Working with the means of the responses is positive to guarantee the independence of the data entered in the ANOVA analysis.

When carrying out the one-factor ANOVA, the quantitative variables obtained from eyetracking were used as dependent variables, such as the number of fixations and fixation time. The qualitative variables obtained from the user test were used as factor variables, such as sex, purchase preference, etc.

2.7. Study of the relative importance of AOIs

To analyse the relative importance of AOIs, the number of fixations and the average fixation time are analysed based on the size or extent of the AOIs, using two indicators. These indicators are our own proposal based on the study by Hyun et al. (2017) (Hyun, Lee, and Kim 2017):

$$Index A = \frac{Number\ of\ fixations}{\%Area} \quad (1)$$

$$Index B = \frac{Time\ of\ fixations}{\%Area} \quad (2)$$

Index A and Index B are indices that analyse the importance of the AOIs based on the number of fixations they receive (Index A) and based on the total duration of the fixations (Index B).

The two indices are directly related, since the greater the number of fixations an AOI receives, the greater the gaze retention time at that AOI. These indices serve to measure the probabilities of fixations per area and thus determine the meaning and visual importance of each area. They are useful for making direct comparisons of one AOI with another and establishing rankings.

3. Results

The main results obtained are shown below, following the methodology described in the previous section and in Figure 2.

3.1. Experiment design

In order to graphically represent the proposed attributes and levels, the morphological chart creativity technique has been applied, since it enables the graphical analysis of the attributes of the product, its variants, and their possible combinations.

The attributes and levels of the proposed product have been defined. An analysis is subsequently carried out to decide which properties (areas of the vehicle) are to be studied, while taking into account that the analysis is based on the front view of the vehicle. For each view, the set of different levels to be considered are determined.

In this case, a sample space is obtained that comprises the different levels of the following properties:

- Headlights shape (5 levels)
- Headlight separation (2 levels)
- Grille shape (6 levels)
- Frontal shape (5 levels)
- Bonnet shape (3 levels)
- Bonnet nerve (3 levels)

The combination of these properties and levels constitutes a sample space of 2,700 in size.

$$\text{Number of products} = 5 \times 2 \times 6 \times 5 \times 3 \times 3 = 2,700.$$

The sample space obtained is too large to be tackled in a survey. The reduction of the sample space is carried out (through orthogonal design, performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics v.26 software).

The orthogonal design experiment carried out with the SPSS software proposed 49 combinations of attribute levels based on the proposed morphological chart. The design team decided to have an equal representation of electric (n=24) and fossil-fuel (n=25) vehicles in the proposed sample space (N=49).

Variable	Categories	n	%
Vehicle propulsion system	Electric	24	49.0
	Fossil fuel	25	51.0

Table 2. Vehicle sample characteristics (N=49).

The graphical representation of the 49 samples obtained is then generated, and for each stimulus (vehicle) the areas of interest (AOIs) are differentiated. For the analysis of the front view of the vehicle, six AOIs have been defined: windscreen, bonnet, right headlight, left headlight, grille, and frontal. These areas are clearly delimited in each of the images obtained. An example of a

sample represented graphically is shown in Figure 4, with its delimited AOIs. There are 49 samples like this.

Figure 4. Definition of AOIs on one of the images used in the experiment frontal.

3.2. Experiments and descriptive analysis of the results

At the beginning of the experiment, the researchers explain the test procedure and the objectives of the study.

Three data collections from the participants have been carried out and therefore three types of results are obtained. In addition to the analysis of each experiment, analysis is carried out to study possible relationships between the data from the three experiments.

3.2.1 User test

In the proposed experiment, 33 respondents of legal age from the university environment have participated, with representatives of both sexes and of various age ranges.

The results obtained from the 7 questions asked in the user test survey are reflected in Table 3 below.

Variables	Categories	n	%
Sex	Female	17	51.5
	Male	16	48.5
Age	Between 18 and 21	8	24.2
	Between 22 and 25	9	27.3
	More than 25	16	48.5
Driving licence	Yes	30	90.9
	In process	3	9.1
Ecological choice	Yes	19	57.6

	No	14	42.4
Purchase preference for a 100%-electric vehicle	Price	6	18.2
	Automatic	19	57.6
	Cargo volume	5	15.2
	Brand	1	3.0
	Power	2	6.1
Desire to purchase a 100%-electric vehicle	Yes	19	57.6
	No	14	42.4
Ability to differentiate a 100%-electric vehicle	Yes	7	21.2
	In doubt	17	51.5
	No	9	27.3

Table 3. Participant characteristics (N=33)

A correlation analysis has been carried out between the variables of the user test and it has been established that there is a slightly statistically significant correlation at the 0.05 level (bilateral) between:

- Age (P2) and possession of the driving licence B1 (P3): $r_{2,3}=-0.352$; $sig_{2,3}=0.045$.
- Purchase preference for a 100%-electric vehicle (P5) and the ability to differentiate a 100%-electric vehicle (P7): $r_{5,7}=-0.351$; $sig_{5,7}=0.046$.

It can be affirmed that all the other variables of the user test are independent of each other.

3.2.2. Eye tracking

An eye-tracking experiment was subsequently carried out, in which the images were shown to the respondents. One of the respondents has been eliminated from the analysis due to errors in the data collection from the eye trackers, thereby leaving 32 respondents: 16 men and 16 women. The oculometry experiment consists of the visualisation of 49 stimuli.

The following variables are obtained from this experiment:

- E1: Fixations (count) for all AOIs
- E2: Total fixation duration mean (ms) for all AOIs
- E3: Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Windscreen
- E4: Fixation duration mean in AOI (ms): Windscreen
- E5: Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Bonnet
- E6: Fixation duration mean (ms) in AOI: Bonnet
- E7: Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Right headlight

- E8: Fixation duration mean (ms) in AOI: Right headlight
- E9: Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Left headlight
- E10: Fixation duration mean (ms) in AOI: Left headlight
- E11: Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Grille
- E12: Fixation duration mean (ms) in AOI: Grille
- E13: Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Frontal
- E14: Fixation duration mean (ms) in AOI: Frontal

The results of the eye-tracking experiment are both quantitative and graphical.

Quantitative results have been obtained regarding the number of fixations per AOI and the duration of fixation (ms) per AOI. For each item of data, the mean value, the standard deviation, and the maximum value have been obtained (the minimum value has not been included because it is equal to zero, since several respondents do not have fixations on certain AOIs).

For the visual or graphic results, heat maps and eye-tracking maps have been used. The heat maps graphically mark the areas of each stimulus with the highest retention of attention (based on the number of fixations and their duration), and the eye-tracking maps or trajectory maps analyse the visual order of the fixations established by the user in each stimulus. The order of the trajectories makes it possible to obtain an index of similarity of the sequence of fixations between respondents.

Vehicles	Areas of interest	Fixation counts			Fixation durations (ms)		
		Mean	SD	Max.	Mean	SD	Max.
All vehicles	Windscreen	1.74	2.22	18	95.66	127.81	838
	Bonnet	5.35	3.98	24	168.03	113.71	895
	Right headlight	0.86	1.14	8	113.18	154.65	1199
	Left headlight	0.93	1.04	6	134.01	170.30	1265
	Grille	4.58	3.78	20	164.87	124.76	920
	Frontal	5.79	4.78	27	166.29	110.23	1134
Electric	Windscreen	1.86	2.36	14	91.81	119.75	624
	Bonnet	5.23	3.77	19	168.13	115.10	805
	Right headlight	0.86	1.15	8	114.32	154.21	854
	Left headlight	0.94	1.04	6	135.76	172.90	1019
	Grille	3.98	3.99	20	145.36	130.46	920
	Frontal	6.69	5.15	27	169.15	102.24	1134

Fossil fuel	Windscreen	1.62	2.07	18	99.36	135.07	838
	Bonnet	5.46	4.16	24	167.94	112.43	895
	Right headlight	0.87	1.14	6	112.08	155.15	1199
	Left headlight	0.91	1.05	5	132.34	167.85	1265
	Grille	5.16	3.48	19	183.59	116.06	870
	Frontal	4.93	4.22	24	163.54	117.38	773

Table 4. Mean values, standard deviation, and maximum value of the fixation counts and total fixation durations in milliseconds (ms) based on defined areas of interest.

Figure 5. Example of heat map for a specific respondent and for all respondents for the vehicle

"Experiment sample 10"

Figure 6. Example of a scan-path map for a specific respondent and for all respondents for the vehicle "Experiment sample 11"

We show below the correlation between parameters of the eye-tracking experiment.

There is a strong negative correlation between “Fixations (count) for all AOIs” (E1) and “Total fixation duration mean (ms) for all AOIs” (E2), which indicates that the greater the number of fixations, the shorter the average time of each fixation: $r_{1,2}=-0.905$; $sig_{1,2}=0.000$.

There is a medium level of correlation between the “Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Right headlight” (E7) and “Fixation duration mean (ms) in AOI: Right headlight” (E8): $r_{7,8}=0.546$; $sig_{7,8}=0.000$.

There is also a medium level of correlation between the “Number of fixations (count) in AOI: Left headlight” (E9) and “Fixation duration mean (ms) in AOI: Left headlight” (E10): $r_{9,10}=0.484$; $sig_{9,10}=0.000$.

Subsequent to these analyses of the correlation between user test variables and the correlation between eye-tracking variables, a series of ANOVAs were performed to analyse possible dependencies between the user test variables (factor variable in ANOVA) and the eye-tracking experiment variables (variables quantitative in ANOVA).

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is based on the statistical assumptions of independence, normality, and homoscedasticity of the experimental responses (Villanueva, Petenate, and Da Silva 2000). As has been argued in the methodology section, the independence condition is met, given that we have worked with a randomised design. The conditions of normality and homoscedasticity must therefore be verified.

Moreover, a correlation analysis has been carried out between the fixations in the different areas, and the correlation matrix shown in Table 5 is obtained, which supports the assumption that the measurements are independent.

	Windscreen (ms)	Bonnet (ms)	Right headlight (ms)	Left headlight (ms)	Grille (ms)	Frontal (ms)
Windscreen (ms)	1.000	0.114	-0.066	-0.016	-0.266	-0.257
Bonnet (ms)	0.114	1.000	-0.007	0.035	-0.300	-0.462
Right headlight (ms)	-0.066	-0.007	1.000	0.194	-0.055	-0.123
Left headlight (ms)	-0.016	0.035	0.194	1.000	-0.088	-0.126
Grille (ms)	-0.266	-0.300	-0.055	-0.088	1.000	-0.256
Frontal (ms)	-0.257	-0.462	-0.123	-0.126	-0.256	1.000

Table 5. Correlation matrix between AOI fixation times

Note that the preceding table is a correlation table based on the Pearson correlation coefficient. This coefficient is a statistical measure that evaluates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables. This coefficient, denoted as r , varies between -1 and 1. When the Pearson correlation coefficient is negative, it indicates a negative correlation between the variables, meaning that as one variable increases, the other decreases in a constant proportion.

The normality (Shapiro Wills) and homoscedasticity (Levene) tests can now be carried out for all pairs of factors analysed. As an example, the case for the Gaze is shown below: fixation (count) and the sex factor.

		Shapiro-Wilk		
	Sex	Statistic	gl	Sig.
Gaze: Fixations (count)	Male	0.941	16	0.356
	Female	0.933	16	0.270

Table 6. Example of results of the normality and homoscedasticity tests (1)

		Levene Statistic	gl1	gl2	Sig.
Gaze: Fixations (count)	Based on the mean	0.400	1	30	0.527
	Based on the median	0.807	1	30	0.369

Table 7. Example of results of the normality and homoscedasticity tests (2)

The ANOVA tests have been carried out and it can be concluded that those analyses in which sig. <0.05 constitute the ANOVAs that meet the alternative hypothesis, and therefore in those cases it can be said that there are significant differences in the variable response regarding the factor levels (with a confidence of 95%). The results in which a relationship has been found in the response depending on the levels of the factor are presented below.

- ANOVA between number of fixations in AOIs vs. type of vehicle

The average number of fixations in the AOIs "windscreen", "Grille", and "Frontal" present significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the vehicle-type factor (E or G).

The number of fixations in the "Windscreen" and "Frontal" AOIs is higher in electric vehicles.

The number of fixations in the “Grille” AOIs is greater in fossil-fuel vehicles.

- ANOVA between number of fixations in AOIs vs. P1: Sex

ANOVA: the number of mean fixations in the AOIs "Bonnet", "Grille" and "Frontal" present significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the sex factor (P1).

In the number of fixations in the AOIs "Bonnet", "Grille" and "Frontal", there are significant differences based on the sex of the respondent.

The number of fixations in the “Bonnet” and “Grille” AOIs is higher in men.

The number of fixations in the “Frontal” AOIs is higher in women.

- ANOVA between number of fixations in AOIs vs. P2: Age

ANOVA: the mean number of fixations in the total AOIs present significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the age factor (P2).

ANOVA: the mean number of fixations in the AOIs “Bonnet”, “Right headlight”, “Left headlight”, and “Frontal” present significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the age factor (P2). In conclusion, younger users between 18 and 21 years of age have more fixations on AOIs Right headlight and Left headlight.

- ANOVA between number of fixations in AOIs vs. P7: Ability to differentiate a 100%-electric vehicle

ANOVA: the mean number of fixations in the total AOIs present significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, regarding the differentiation factor between vehicles (P7).

ANOVA: the mean number of fixations in the AOIs "Windscreen", "Bonnet", " Right headlight", and " Left headlight" present significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, regarding the differentiation preference between vehicles (P7). Specifically, the users who have responded as to whether they are able to differentiate an electric vehicle from another vehicle that is not electric, present a greater number of fixations in the AOIs “Right headlight” and “Left headlight”.

- ANOVA between mean duration of fixations (ms) in AOIs vs. type of vehicle

ANOVA: the average fixation time in the "Grille" AOIs presents significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the type of vehicle (E/G).

The average fixation time in the "Grille" AOIs is greater in fossil-fuel vehicles.

- ANOVA between mean duration of fixations (ms) in AOIs vs. P1: Sex

ANOVA: the average fixation time in the AOIs presents significant differences in the headlights (Right headlight and Left headlight), with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the respondent's sex (P1).

The mean fixation time in the AOIs "Right headlight" and "Left headlight" is greater for men.

- ANOVA between mean duration of fixations (ms) in AOIs vs. P2: Age

ANOVA: the mean fixation time in the AOIs presents significant differences in all areas of interest, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the respondent's age (P2).

As a separate conclusion, in all the AOIs, the users aged over 25 are those with significantly lower mean fixation times than the other 2 user groups.

- ANOVA between mean duration of fixations (ms) in AOIs vs. P4: Ecological choice

ANOVA: the mean fixation time in the AOIs presents significant differences in all the areas of interest except in the "Frontal" AOI, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to ecological awareness (P4).

As a general conclusion, those surveyed who are not ecologically aware when purchasing vehicles have higher average fixation times.

- ANOVA between mean duration of fixations (ms) in AOIs vs. P5: Purchase preference for a 100%-electric vehicle.

ANOVA: the mean fixation time in the AOIs presents significant differences in all the areas of interest with the exception of the AOI "Windscreen", with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to purchase preference (P5).

Users whose purchase preference is the "Brand" have had a longer average fixation time in the AOIs "Right headlight", "Left headlight", and "Bonnet". For users whose preference is "Price" they have had a greater fixation for the AOI "Grille".

- ANOVA between mean duration of fixations (ms) in AOIs vs. P6: Desire to purchase a 100%-electric vehicle.

ANOVA: the mean fixation time in the AOIs presents significant differences in all the areas of interest with the exception of the AOI "Right headlight" and "Grille", with a confidence level of 95%, compared to the purchase of a 100%-electric vehicle (P6).

As a general conclusion, respondents who plan to purchase a 100%-electric car have higher average fixation times.

- ANOVA between mean duration of fixations (ms) in AOIs vs. P7: Ability to differentiate a 100%-electric vehicle.

ANOVA: the mean fixation time in the AOIs presents significant differences in all areas of interest, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the ability to differentiate a 100%-electric vehicle (P7).

As a general conclusion, those surveyed who have answered that they are able to ascertain whether a vehicle is electric or not by its aesthetic-formal appearance have higher mean fixation times. Respondents who have answered that they are unable to ascertain whether a vehicle is electric or not due to its aesthetic-formal appearance have lower average fixation times.

3.3.3. Vehicle-type identification

During the eye-tracking experiment, the results of which are described in the previous section, respondents were asked to answer whether they think it is an electric or fossil-fuel car. In this experiment, the data collected relate to hits and misses in vehicle recognition.

Summary	Mean	SD	Max.	Min.
Hits	33.7	4.07	40	22
Misses	15.3	4.07	27	9

Table 8. Summary of hits and misses per user

Only one respondent has a hit rate below 50%.

Vehicle propulsion system	n	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.
Electric	24	21.00	8.612	3	31
Fossil fuel	25	24.32	6.095	11	33
Total	49	22.69	7.545	3	33

Table 9. Summary of hits per vehicle propulsion system

Having carried out a series of ANOVAs, the following results are obtained:

- The number of hits and misses in the eye-tracking test is independent of the type of vehicle (electric or fossil fuel). The average number of hits in fossil-fuel vehicles is slightly higher than the average number of hits in electric vehicles.
- The number of correct answers presents significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, regarding the factor Ability to differentiate a 100%-electric vehicle (P7). The average number of correct answers is higher in those surveyed who have answered that they are able to recognise an electric vehicle. The average number of correct answers is less for the respondents who have answered that they are unable to recognise an electric vehicle. This variable (P7) is the only variable related to the number of hits, which is an indicator that users have answered honestly regarding their recognition ability.
- The number of hits presents significant differences, with a confidence level of 95%, with respect to the number of fixations on the grille (Number of fixations in AOI: Grille). The mean number of fixations in the AOI: Grille is significantly higher in vehicles that have missed than in vehicles that have hit (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Number of fixations in AOI: Grille

3.4. Study of the relative importance of AOIs

As indicated in the methodology section, in order to analyse the relative importance of the AOIs, the number of fixations and the average fixation time based on the size or extension of the AOIs are analysed through two indicators, which provide the main innovation of this work.

To this end, firstly, a correlation analysis has been carried out:

Variables to correlate:

- SIZE_AOI
- Complete fixation time in AOI (ms).
- Number of fixations in AOI.
- Fixation duration mean in AOI.

All correlations are significant, especially that of the number of fixations in the AOI with the size of the AOI. Taking into account the size of the AOI, it should be noted that this variable has a correlation coefficient of 0.707 with the number of fixations in the AOI, which is an indicator that the number of fixations, as well as their average duration, is highly correlated with the AOI size.

SIZE_AOI	Complete fixation time in AOI (ms)	Number of fixations in AOI	Fixation duration mean in AOI
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Correlation	SIZE_AOI	1.000	0.640	0.707	0.334
	Complete fixation time in AOI (ms)	0.640	1.000	0.984	0.744
	Number of fixations in AOI	0.707	0.984	1.000	0.679
	Fixation duration mean in AOI	0.334	0.744	0.679	1.000

*All the following=0.00

Table 10. Correlation matrix using Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Figures 8 and 9 below show the results of the proposed indices A and B for the various AOIs.

Figure 8. Cumulative number of fixations for each AOI

The AOIs that accumulate the greatest number of fixations per area size (Figure 7) are:

1. Grille
2. Left headlight (F2)
3. Right headlight (F1)

Likewise, the AOIs that accumulate the longest fixation time per area size (Figure 8) are:

1. Left headlight (F2)
2. Grille
3. Right headlight (F1)

It can be determined that these areas are the most important for users when deciding whether a vehicle is electric or combustion-powered.

Figure 9. Accumulated fixation time for each AOI

4. Discussion

4.1. Regarding the sample size used for the experiment.

This section presents a discussion based on certain reference texts on the topic under study.

Regarding the design of the eye-tracking experiment, 10 texts have been analysed (see Table 11).

Reference	Content	Sample size and composition
(Luo et al. 2022)	Research on the aesthetic preferences of users for the design of the shape of the rear lights of vehicles through eye tracking.	n= 46 (23 women, 23 men)
(Hyun, Lee, and Kim 2017)	Evaluation of automobile exterior designs through eye tracking to obtain shape similarities and novel design elements.	n= not specified
(Lin, Guo, and Xu 2019)	Investigation of the perceived experiences through the formal aesthetic design of intelligent vehicles through eye tracking and semantic analysis.	n= 89
(Wickman et al. 2014)	Eye-tracking analysis of the influence of assembly lines between bodywork elements on the perception of a vehicle.	n= 31 (5 women, 26 men)
(Lu, Xu, and Cheng 2018)	Objective evaluation by users on the formal design of vehicles through eye tracking for the extraction of properties.	n= 11 (7 men, 4 women)

(Moon et al. 2021)	Analysis by eye tracking and electroencephalography of the visual impression of vehicle fronts.	n= 12 (10 men, 2 women)
(Purucker, Sprott, and Herrmann 2014)	Investigation through eye tracking of user reactions to vehicle fronts with "aggressive" ("threatening") design.	n= 39 (13 women, 26 men)
(Chang, Chu, and Ma 2013)	Eye-tracking analysis of the front appearance of cars to analyse the main areas of interest.	n= 20
(Köhler, Falk, and Schmitt 2015)	Product design by Kansei Engineering with eye-tracking techniques to evaluate the perception and areas of interest of users.	n= not specified
(Köhler, Falk, and Schmitt 2013)	Analysis and identification of relevant components of the product and linking with semantic concepts using eye tracking.	n= 11

Table 11. References

No consensus exists on the exposure time of each stimulus or image, although it can be established as varying between 3 and 20 seconds. Several texts include a blank image between images for usually between 0.1 and 5 seconds. Concerning the definition of how long a fixation lasts is included in only one text, which establishes it as being 100ms. There are studies in which the respondent must make a decision as to whether the stimulus they see is "type A" or "type B", for which two letters on the keyboard are used.

In order to prevent the respondent from looking at the keyboard when they press a key, thereby losing information in the eye tracking, our experiment commands the researcher to write down what they think without looking up from the monitor.

Regarding the sample size, the texts analysed seldom use a very large size, and vary between approximately 11 and 89 participants, the majority being at about 25 respondents. We therefore consider the sample size used (33 participants) to be highly suitable for this type of experiment.

4.2. Suggestions to develop optimal designs aligned with user perception.

According to the capital value pyramid of Keller's customer-based brand equity model (see Figure 10) (Keller 2008), brand prominence measures the awareness thereof; for example, how often and how easily the brand is evoked in different situations or circumstances. Brand awareness refers to the customer's ability to remember and

recognise the brand under a variety of conditions, with certain associations in memory. In particular, building brand awareness helps the consumer understand the product or service category in which it competes and what products or services are sold under its name. It also ensures that customers know which of their “needs” (through these products) the brand is designed to satisfy.

Figure 10. Capital value pyramid of Keller’s customer-based brand equity model. Adapted from (Keller 2008)

Brand awareness gives the product an identity by linking its elements with a product category, associated purchase, and situations of use or consumption. The depth of brand awareness measures how likely a brand element is to come to mind, and how easily it does so. Breadth in turn measures the variety of purchase and use situations in which the brand element comes to mind and further deepens the brand’s organisation and product knowledge in memory (Branch 2001).

This work aims to provide ideas and suggestions to develop optimal designs aligned with user perception. As argued by Branch (2011), building brand awareness helps the consumer understand the category of the product or service in which it competes and what products or services are sold under its name, thereby granting the product an

identity by linking its elements with a category of products, associated purchase, and situations of use or consumption. Therefore, the identity of the electric vehicle must focus on enhancing those properties that give the electric car a differentiating character.

In the previous section it is shown that the AOIs that accumulate the greatest number of fixations per area size and the longest fixation time are the Grille, the Left headlight, and the Right headlight. These areas are therefore the most important for users when deciding whether a vehicle is electric or combustion-powered.

The suggestions to develop optimal designs aligned with user perception are aimed at focusing on enhancing those properties that give the electric car a differentiating character, that is, they focus the design of electric cars on those areas most important for users when deciding whether a vehicle is electric or combustion-powered: the Grille, the Left headlight, and the Right headlight.

5. Conclusions

Promoting the electric car is one way to address the environmental and sustainability challenges facing transport, since the electrification of transport can play a major role in the transition towards a more sustainable and cleaner energy system.

There are numerous publications that have studied how the aesthetic properties of the car can affect consumer perception of whether it is electric or combustion-powered, and how these perceptions can be utilised to improve market acceptance of electric vehicles (Hypothesis 1).

In this work, we have studied how individual differences in perception and attention can affect the most significant areas of a vehicle, and how these findings can be employed to improve the design and user experience. Eye tracking has been utilised to analyse user interaction with complex visualisations, such as network graphs and flowcharts.

Through the application of eye tracking, it has been determined which areas of an image (in this case images of vehicles) are more influential in the perception of it as either being electric or combustion-powered (Hypothesis 2)

It has been analysed how the most important areas of a vehicle and the perceptions of users regarding said vehicle can differ depending on gender and other socio-demographic variables (Hypothesis 3).

Numerous reference texts have been analysed and are found to seldom use a very large sample size. Therefore, it is considered that the sample size used herein of 33 participants is highly suitable for this type of experiment.

To determine the relative importance of the AOIs, the number of fixations and the average fixation time based on the size or extent of the AOIs are analysed through two indicators. These indicators provide the main innovation of this work.

The AOIs that accumulate the most fixations per area size are the grille and the two headlights. It can therefore be determined that these areas are the most important for users when deciding on whether a vehicle is either an electric or a combustion-powered car.

This work provides an experimental design and a way to analyze and draw conclusions from an oculometry study for vehicles, as well as an initial design briefing for the generation of the visual identity of electric vehicles based on the perception of user for different elements of the vehicle.

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